

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18215147>

LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF THE LEXICON RELATED TO INTERNET ADVERTISING

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ABSTRACT

Advertising has an impact on everyone's everyday lives as technology has advanced and mass media has become more diverse. Language is the primary message carrier in all types of advertising. Advertising language differs from ordinary language. It is a style of immediate impact and rapid persuade. Advertising language has various grammatical, pragmatic and functional characteristics that separate it from other varieties, both specialized and non-specialized. This study work attempts to give an analysis of advertising language from the perspective of linguistic and pragmatic elements of the lexicon, as well as to identify linguistic means utilized in advertising texts.

Keywords: *advertising, linguistic features, slogan, specialized discourse, lexicon*

INTRODUCTION

The gradual change of digital technologies has shaped the growth of advertisements. In particular, it has emerged as a powerful means of persuasion of social media, websites and mobile applications and unlike traditional advertisements,

online ones rely on visual imaginary as well as linguistic and pragmatic strategies tailored to the digital technology.

The linguistic dimension of internet advertising has attracted increasing attention from researchers in pragmatics, discourse analysis and sociolinguistics. The lexicon of internet advertisements reflects the fusion of language economy, creativity and strategic intent. Linguopragmatics, the intersection of linguistics and pragmatics, provides a useful framework for understanding how lexical choices serve communicative purposes, such as persuasion, identification, and engagement. This paper aims to analyze the linguopragmatic features of the lexicon used in internet advertising, focusing on the interplay between lexical meaning, pragmatic function, and contextual factors.

Theoretical background

Linguopragmatics analyzes the way linguistic forms convey meaning in certain, specific backgrounds and contexts. In the case of advertising, it involves understanding of how words and expressions influence the audience's responses. According to G.Leech,¹ pragmatic meaning exceed the literal meaning with the certain levels of implied intentions, emotions and values.

The discourse of advertising is inherently persuasive. It is designed to inform and affect behavior and attitudes. Advertising language is a mix of cognitive, aesthetic and social functions that appeal to logic and emotion according to G.Cook.² Internet advertising is different from traditional form of media because it encourages interaction. The user is receiver and participant simultaneously, from liking, commenting, sharing to skipping content.

Lexical items in online advertisements include three important tendencies: Economy – the use of short, impactful words and phrases: Shop now; Stay fresh; Get yours; Innovation – the production of new words or blending existing ones:

¹ Leech G. *Principles of Pragmatics*. – London: Longman, 1983. – P. 233.

² Cook G. *The Discourse of Advertising*. – London: Routledge, 2001. – P. 256.

instaworthy, clickbait, glowup; Interactivity – to address the reader directly: You deserve better; Join us; Let's go.

Methodology

A qualitative linguistic analysis based on examples from diverse internet advertising platforms such as Instagram, Youtube and Google are adopted into the research. A corpus of fifteen words are analyzed to identify the features of lexical and pragmatic aspects. According to Goddard A,¹ each word is examined for:

- Lexical patterns: *word formation, connotation, novelty*;
- Pragmatic functions: *speech acts, implicature and emotional appeal*;
- Contextual relevance: relationship between brand identity and target audience.

Findings and discussion

Internet advertising tends to utilize simple, minimalistic language. Advertisers favor elliptical constructions and one-line slogans due to the limited space and short attention spans. For example:

“Be unstoppable” – Femina;

“Less talk, more glow” – Ledneonz;

“Find your vibe” – CTvisit.

In such phrases the combination of imperatives and adjectives create inspirational and emotional resonance. The function of linguopragmatics here is directive, urging, expressive to convey action and attitude.

Online advertisements are dominated by emotionally charged words which shows the reflection of shift from logical persuasion to effective influence. The common lexical items include:

- Positive adjectives: *amazing, exclusive, ultimate, perfect, effortless, smart*;
- Emotive verbs: *love, transform, enjoy, feel, discover*.

These items create positive environment and emotional alignment between brand and customer. Such words pragmatically perform the function of softening persuasion

¹ Goddard A. *The Language of Advertising: Written Texts*. – London: Routledge, 2002. – P. 192.

for the natural or spontaneous interaction according to Crystal D.¹ Word creation is a major feature of internet advertising lexicon which includes blending, clipping and combining English roots with brand-related elements. For example: *textpectation* (*text* + *expectation*) = *iPhone/ Samsung Ads*; *promo* (*Promotion*) = *Amazon / Shein / Shopee*. Such lexical neologisms serve both pragmatic and aesthetic purposes. They capture attention, signal creativity and align with the playful, meme-driven culture of digital media.

Myers G² emphasizes that pronouns like *you*, *your* and *we* are central to internet advertising. They establish a conversational tone and simulate interpersonal connection. For example: “*We’ve got you covered.*” “*Your skin deserves better.*” “*Join our family today.*”

Pragmatically, these constructions imply inclusion and trust, key to building brand-consumer relationships. Internet advertisements blend linguistic and visual codes (typography, colors and foreign words). Code switching (“*C’est chic!*”, “*Hola summer!*”) adds structure, while visual-linguistic combinations adds pragmatic meaning. The interplay of these produces a richer semiotic impact than the text.

Conclusion

The lexicon of advertising showcases a complex interplay of linguistic creativity and pragmatic intention. Words are chosen for their denotative meaning, emotional change, cultural connotation and interaction potential. Lexical economy, direct imperatives, emotional vocabulary, neologisms, conversational tone are identified as the main linguopragmatic features. They reflect the importance of online, fast, emotional communication. Future research could expand on cross-cultural variations in internet advertising language and explore the impact of AI-generated on linguistic creativity and authenticity.

¹ Crystal D. *Language and the Internet*. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006. – P. 304.

² Myers G. *Words in Ads*. – London: Edward Arnold, 1994. – P. 208.

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